

CURING OF THE EPOXY RESINS UNDER MICROWAVE AND/OR ELECTRON BEAM TREATMENT

H. Iovu¹, I. Calinescu¹, M. Radoiu², D. Martin², E. Mateescu²

¹*Department of Polymer Science & Composites, Polytechnic University of Bucharest, 149 Calea Victoriei, 71101-Bucharest, Romania*

²*Electron Accelerator Laboratory, National Institute for Lasers, Plasma and Radiation Physics, P.O.Box MG-36, 76900-Bucharest, Romania*

KEYWORDS: epoxy resins curing, microwave, electron beam, curing agents.

INTRODUCTION

The use of polymer composite materials in the mass production of industrial components is limited by the extent of the thermal process time due to the very low thermal conductivity of polymer materials. Besides, heat supply for thermoset polymer curing occurs from the components external surface by means of hot press or hot air and so leads to a heterogeneous thermal treatment. Thermal heating inside an oven classically activates the crosslinking of the epoxy resins and molds are resorted. Recently new techniques of activation based on the electromagnetic irradiation of polymer matrix are developed.

In this paper we reported data concerning the crosslinking process of the DGEBA epoxy resin type under microwave (MW) and/or electron beam (EB) treatment using triethylenetetramine (TETA) as a curing agent.

EXPERIMENTAL

Mixtures (~25g) of DGEBA with variable amounts of curing agent were introduced into a cylindrical reactor made from glass, which was then placed into the reaction chamber. The curing process was registered as the temperature increasing in time.

The microwave applicator was a rectangular cavity of 245 mm x 245 mm x 450 mm. The microwave power is coupled via one of its sidewalls with a slotted rectangular waveguide (five inclined series slots cut in the broad wall of a WR430 waveguide and spaced $1/2 \lambda_G$ apart). The electron beam from a linear accelerator, ALIN-10, of 6 MeV and 70 W maximum output power, is introduced perpendicularly by the upper-end of the rectangular cavity passing an aluminum window of 100 μm thick.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The new architecture of the reaction chamber (RC) provides a high microwave energy transfer and a very good electrical field uniformity. Therefore the results obtained by microwave treatment in this chamber are better than those obtained in a modified domestic oven (MDO) (Fig. 1). The use of the RC applicator allows the possibility to study the effects of microwave and/or electron beam treatment on the curing process. Due to the small volume of the samples (~25 ml), the value of microwave power was 30 W and the total absorbed dose was about 20 kGy (with a dose rate of 1 kGy/min).

Fig.1: The influence of the microwave applicator type on the curing of the DGEBA epoxy resins

In order to determine the absorbed power for the three irradiation treatments, samples without TETA were used. One may observe that the increasing of temperature is much higher in the case of microwave treatment than for the electron beam treatment. For using 7% TETA, the increasing of temperature was more significant due to the curing process. Also, by simultaneously treatment with electron beam and microwave power, the curing process occurs in a small time period (Fig. 2).

Fig.2: The influence of the curing agent concentration and the irradiation type on the curing process of the DGEBA epoxy resin

Attempts to use other curing agents, DEA (diethylamine) and NNDA (N,N-diethylaniline) result in a product with a very low degree of crosslinking. The explanation for DEA and NNDA behavior has to consider the molecular structure of these two curing agents. The nitrogen atoms in their molecules have less or even no hydrogen atoms linked, which could attack and open the epoxy rings. Thus they need a higher temperature for the crosslinking process to be developed. This temperature is reached after a long time in which almost all the solvent has gone. The lack of the solvent will strongly hinder the crosslinking process of the epoxy resin.

As a conclusion, by combination of electron beam and microwave power, a better curing process was developed, thus the curve of crosslinking being closer to the classical system.